

Character Association and Path Analysis of Exotic Bread Wheat (*Triticum Aestivum* L.) Genotypes for Yield and Related Traits at Kokate and Hossana, Southern Ethiopia

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Abstract

Correlations and path coefficients were studied in 48 exotic and 1 recently released bread wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) Genotypes for 11 yield contributing characters. The correlation coefficients were determined to find out the inter relationship among the characters studied. Grain yield was found highly significant and positively correlated with number of kernels per spike ($r_g = 0.303$, $r_p = 0.261$), biological yield ($r_g = 0.561$, $r_p = 0.531$), thousand seed weight ($r_g = 0.317$, $r_p = 0.274$) and harvest index ($r_g = 0.446$, $r_p = 0.416$), which indicated that grain yield could be increased by improving these traits. In order to obtain an understandable picture of the inter relationship between grain yield and its components, direct and indirect effects were measured using path coefficient analysis. Biological yield exhibited the highest positive direct effect (0.913) on grain yield followed by harvest index (0.835). The traits showed high positive direct effect on grain yield indicated that direct selection for these traits might be effective and there is a possibility of improving grain yield through selection based on these traits. The genotypic path coefficient analysis exhibited the residual value of 0.32 indicating that 68% of the variability in grain yield was contributed by characters considered in the path analysis study and the remaining 32% was the contribution of other characters which were not considered in the path analysis and environmental factors. This further elaborated that the choice of yield attributing characters in the study was quite better, even if other characters are also needed to justify grain yield in bread wheat.

Keywords: Bread wheat, Correlation coefficients, grain yield, path coefficient analysis, residual effect.

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Introduction

The degree of association between characters with grain yield as indicated by the correlation coefficients has always been a helpful instrument for the selection of desirable characters that simultaneously increases grain yield under a breeding program (Islam, et al., 2010). Grain yield is the result of many characters that are interdependent. Grain yield, which is the major economic character in wheat, depends on several component traits, which are mutually related. Breeders always look for characters are related with the important characters like yield. Correlation coefficients, although very useful in quantifying the size and direction of trait associations can be genetic variation among traits to select desirable types. Some of these characters are highly associated among themselves and with grain yield. The analysis of the relationship

among these characters and their association with grain yield is essential to establish selection criteria (Singh *et al.*, 1990).

Thus, it is essential to conduct a comparative study of important characters in order to select the most desirable ones. Correlation coefficient alone cannot give a complete picture of the causal basis of relationship. Under such circumstances, path coefficient analysis is an effective tool (Islam and Khan, 1991 and McGiffen *et al.*, 1994). Therefore, the present study was undertaken to estimate the associations among desired traits and their direct and indirect contributions to yield.

Materials and Methods

The experiment was conducted at Kokate and Hossana which are located in Wolaita and Hadya Zones, SNNPR of Ethiopia, respectively. The locations were assumed to represent the major and potential bread wheat production areas of Ethiopia. The sub-stations, Kokate and Hossana are located at 378 Km and 232 Km from Addis Ababa, respectively and both sub-stations are two of the research sites administered by Areka Agricultural Research Center (ArARC). The experiment was carried out under rain fed conditions in 2018/2019 cropping season. In this study, a total of 49 bread wheat genotypes of which 48 ICARDA origins which are selected randomly and one recently released variety, all received from Kulumsa Agricultural Research Centers (KARC) were included. The genotypes were developed at ICARDA for optimum/potential areas to be further tested in mid- to highlands of Ethiopia for high yield potential, resistance to disease and insect pests.

Experimental Design and Trial Management

Field experiment was laid out in 7x7 simple lattice designs in each location. The plot size was 2.5m long and 1.2 m wide (3m²) with 6 rows. The space between replications, plots and rows was 2m, 0.5 m and 0.2m, respectively.

The experiment was conducted in 2018/2019 cropping season. As per the recommendation of the study area, a seed rate of 150Kg/ha (45g per plot) was used. Fertilizer, Urea 150Kg/ha and NPS also 100 Kg/ha or 45 and 30 g/plot were applied, respectively. All the NPS (100 kg/ha) was applied at sowing. Urea was applied in two split: one third at sowing, and the remaining two third just after 35-40 days of sowing (ATA and EIAR, 2007). Hand weeding was used for weed control and all other agronomic practices were undertaken uniformly.

Figure 1. Field Performance of Bread Wheat Genotypes Used for the Study at Different Growth Stages

Data Collection

Data were recorded according to the International Board for Plant Genetic Resources (IBPGR, 1985) revised descriptor lists for wheat. Data were collected both on plot and plant bases. The four central rows were used for data collection on plot basis; whereas five randomly taken plants from the four central rows of each plot were used for data collection on plant basis. Mean data of the five sample plants were used for data analyses.

Results and Discussion

Estimation of Correlation Coefficients

Phenotypic and genotypic association between all possible pair of quantitative character was performed using SAS software version 9.3 (SAS, 2012). In the present study, grain yield showed varying trends of association with yield components at both genotypic and phenotypic levels (Table 1 - Appendix).

The range of genotypic correlation was from -0.001 for days to maturity to 0.561 for biological yield where as phenotypic correlation from 0.011 for grain filling period to 0.531 for biological yield. The analysis revealed that grain yield had positive and significant association with number of kernels per spike ($r_g = 0.303$, $r_p = 0.261$), biological yield ($r_g = 0.561$, $r_p = 0.531$), thousand seed weight ($r_g = 0.317$, $r_p = 0.274$) and harvest index ($r_g = 0.446$, $r_p = 0.416$). This signified that the improvement of one character will simultaneously improve the other.

Results from the present study go in line with the results reported by Kashif and Khaliq (2004), Obsa (2014), Kifle *et al.* (2016), and Kumar *et al.* (2016). These authors reported significant and positive correlation of grain yield with biological yield, harvest index and thousand seed weight in bread wheat genotypes.

Path Coefficient Analysis

The direct and indirect effect of yield related traits on yield was computed through Path coefficient analysis. The analysis was conducted following the method suggested by Dewey and Lu, (1959) using the phenotypic as well as genotypic correlation coefficients to govern the direct and indirect effects of yield components on grain yield based on the following relationship:

$$r_{ij} = P_{ij} + \sum r_{ik}p_{kj} \quad (1)$$

Where,

r_{ij} = mutual association between the independent trait (i) and dependent trait (j) as measured by the correlation coefficient,

P_{ij} = Component of direct effects of the independent trait (i) on the dependent variable (j) measured by the path coefficient, $\sum r_{ik}p_{kj}$ = Summation of components of indirect effect of a given independent trait (i) on the given dependent trait (j) by all other independent traits (k) and the contribution of the remaining unknown characters measured residual effect estimated by the formula as follows:

Residual effect = $\sqrt{1 - R^2}$ Where: - $R^2 = \sum p_{ij}r_{ij}$, R^2 is the residual factor, P_{ij} is the direct effect of yield by i^{th} characters and r_{ij} is the correlation of yield with the i^{th} characters.

In current study, traits that showed significant correlation with grain yield were advanced to path coefficient analysis both at genotypic and phenotypic levels. The results of path analysis for direct and

indirect effects of the characters studied both at genotypic and phenotypic levels are illustrated in Tables 2 and 3, respectively.

Genotypic Path Coefficient Analysis

The results of path coefficient analysis at genotypic level is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Genotypic Path Coefficient Analysis Direct (Diagonal) and Indirect (Off Diagonal) Effect of the Characters

Variables	KPS	BY	TSW	HI	Rg
KPS	0.018	0.273	0.001	0.011	0.303*
BY	0.005	0.913	0.004	-0.361	0.561**
TSW	0.000	0.129	0.026	0.162	0.317*
HI	0.000	-0.394	0.005	0.835	0.446**

Note: Residual = 0.32, * = significant at $p \leq 0.05$, ** = highly significant at $p \leq 0.01$, KPS = number of kernels per spike, BY = biological yield (kg/plot), TSW = thousand seed weight (gm), HI = harvest index (%), rg = genotypic correlation of the character with grain yield.

The results revealed that biological yield exhibited the highest positive direct effect (0.913) on grain yield followed by harvest index (0.835), indicated that the positive and significant correlation of biomass yield and harvest index with grain yield at genotypic level was due to the direct effect of these characters on grain yield. Similar results were reported in bread wheat genotypes by James *et al.* (2017), who obtained maximum positive direct of biological yield followed by harvest index. Some other authors (Obsa, 2014; Dargicho *et al.*, 2015) were also reported similar results.

The lowest positive direct effect was exhibited by kernels per spike (0.018), indicating that the positive association of kernels per spike with grain yield was due to the indirect effect of this character on yield through other characters such as biomass yield and harvest index. This shows the importance of considering harvest index and biomass yield when selection of wheat genotypes for higher grain yield is desired. Similarly, Endashaw (2018) reported the lowest positive direct of kernels per spike on grain yield in bread wheat genotypes. Conversely, Obsa (2014) reported maximum negative direct effect of kernels per spike on grain yield followed by days to heading and grain filling period.

The direct genotypic effect of kernels per spike was positive (0.018). The maximum positive indirect effect of kernels per spike was scored via biological yield (0.273) where as the lowest was scored through thousand seed weight (0.001) followed by harvest index (0.011). The present study go in line with Kifle *et al.* (2016), who reported positive direct effect of kernels per spike on grain yield and they reported maximum positive indirect effect of kernels per spike via biological yield. On the contrary, Abderrahmane *et al.* (2013) realized negative direct effect of kernels per spike on grain yield and the maximum indirect effect was observed through harvest index followed by straw yield, thousand seed weight, and spike number per plant. The same authors reported negative indirect effect on grain yield with biological yield in bread wheat genotypes under semi arid conditions.

As indicated in Table 2, the direct effect of biological yield on grain yield was positive (0.913) indicating that considering biological yield during genotype selection could result significant improvement in grain yield. In other words, biological yield had positive effect on grain yield via kernels per spike and thousand seed weight with respective values of 0.005 and 0.004. However, its indirect effect on grain yield via harvest index was recorded negative with the value -0.361. Similar results were reported by Abderrahmane *et al.* (2013) in wheat genotypes and reported the positive direct effect of biological yield

on grain yield and the positive indirect effect of biological yield through number of grains per spike and thousand seed weight. Similarly, its indirect effect on grain yield via harvest was reported as negative.

Furthermore, James *et al.* (2017) reported positive direct effect of biological yield on grain yield and also reported indirectly biological yield had positive effect on grain yield through thousand seed weight. Similar to the present findings, the same author also reported the indirect effect of biological yield on grain yield through harvest index was recorded as negative value.

The results of path coefficient analysis also revealed that direct effect of thousand seed weight on grain yield was positive (0.026) which is similar to the finding reported by Endashaw (2018). However, Obsa *et al.* (2017) reported negative direct effect of the character on grain yield. The indirect effect of kernels per spike, biological yield and harvest index were found positive.

The direct effect of harvest index on grain yield was positive (0.835). The indirect effect of kernels per spike and thousand seed weight through harvest index on grain yield were positive where as the indirect effect of biological yield on grain yield via harvest index was scored as negative. Several authors reported similar results to the present findings (Abderrahmane *et al.*, 2013; Obsa *et al.*, 2017; Sabit *et al.*, 2017).

The residual effect in the present study was 0.32, implying that 68 % of the variability in grain yield was contributed by characters considered in the path analysis study whereas the remaining 32% is the contribution of other characters which are not considered in the path analysis and environmental factors. This further elaborate that the choice of yield attributing characters in the study was quite better, even if other characters are also needed to justify grain yield in bread wheat.

Phenotypic Path Coefficient Analysis

The results of path coefficient analysis at phenotypic level is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Phenotypic Path Coefficient Analysis Direct (Diagonal) and Indirect (Off Diagonal) Effect of the Characters

Variables	KPS	BY	TSW	HI	rp
KPS	0.026	0.237	-0.001	-0.001	0.261**
BY	0.007	0.906	0.006	-0.388	0.531**
TSW	-0.001	0.123	0.042	0.110	0.274**
HI	0.000	-0.422	0.006	0.832	0.416**

Note: Residual effect = 0.39, ** = highly significant at $p \leq 0.01$, KPS = number of kernels per spike, BY = biological yield (kg/plot), TSW = thousand seed weight (gm), HI = harvest index (%), rp = phenotypic correlation of the character with grain yield.

Conclusion

Phenotypic path coefficient analysis revealed that biological yield (0.906) and harvest index (0.832) exerted high and favorable direct effects on grain yield. This justifies the presence of true relationship between these characters and grain yield as depicted by positive and significant correlations of grain yield with harvest index and biological yield there by direct selection through these characters would result reasonable effect on grain yield. Similar finding was also reported by James *et al.* (2017). But, the lowest positive direct effect at phenotypic level was displayed by kernels per spike (0.026). The highest positive indirect effect at this level was exerted by biological yield (0.237) through kernels per spike. In other cases, the highest negative indirect effect on grain yield was also recorded by biological yield (-0.422) via harvest index. From the present result, biological yield had highest positive and highly significant

correlation with grain yield ($r_p = 0.531$) with its positive and negative indirect effects through other characters which counter balance each other and result in this high association with grain yield.

The study also revealed that direct effect of kernels per spike on grain yield was positive (0.026). The maximum positive indirect effect of kernels per spike (0.237) on grain yield was recorded through biological yield as described earlier and the negative indirect effect of kernels per spike (-0.001) were recorded via thousand seed weight and harvest index in similar magnitude.

The phenotypic path coefficient analysis showed that direct effect of biological yield on grain yield was positive (0.906). In directly, biological yield had positive effect on grain yield via kernels per spike (0.007) and thousand seed weight (0.006). But, the negative indirect effect of biological yield on grain yield (-0.388) were scored through harvest index. Thousand seed weight had direct effect of (0.042) and its indirect effect on grain yield were recorded via biological yield, harvest index and kernels per spike with respective value of 0.123, 0.110 and -0.001. The direct effect of harvest index on grain yield was 0.832. Its indirect effect on grain yield obtained via thousand seed weight, kernels per spike and biological yield (0.006, 0.000 and -0.422), respectively (Table 3).

The phenotypic path coefficient analysis exhibited the residual value of 0.39 indicating that 61% of the variability in grain yield was contributed by characters considered in the path analysis study and the remaining 39% was the contribution of other characters which were not considered in the path analysis and environmental factors.

Author Contribution Statement

Mathewos Chumamo Bunaro: conceived, designed and performed the experiments, analyzed and interpreted the data, wrote the paper.

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Declaration of Interest's Statement

The author declare no conflict of interest.

Additional Information

No additional information is available for this paper.

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Appendix

Table 1. Genotypic (Above Diagonal) and Phenotypic (Below Diagonal) Correlation Coefficients of 49 Bread Wheat Genotypes Evaluated for 11 Quantitative Traits at Kokate and Hossana, SNNPR, 2018/19 Cropping Season

Traits	HD	GFP	MD	PH	SL	KPS	SPS	BY	TSW	HI	GY
HD		-0.116 ^{ns}	0.633 ^{**}	0.041 ^{ns}	0.339 [*]	0.273 ^{ns}	0.520 ^{**}	0.479 ^{**}	0.065 ^{ns}	0.537 ^{**}	-0.045 ^{ns}
GFP	-0.104 ^{ns}		0.696 ^{**}	0.013 ^{ns}	0.269 ^{ns}	-0.060 ^{ns}	0.145 ^{ns}	0.142 ^{ns}	0.220 ^{ns}	-0.006 ^{ns}	0.041 ^{ns}
MD	0.604 ^{**}	0.730 ^{**}		0.040 ^{ns}	0.455 ^{**}	0.150 ^{ns}	0.489 ^{**}	0.457 ^{**}	0.125 ^{ns}	-0.393 ^{**}	-0.001 ^{ns}
PH	0.045 ^{ns}	0.015 ^{ns}	0.043 ^{ns}		0.148 ^{ns}	0.030 ^{ns}	-0.061 ^{ns}	0.127 ^{ns}	0.285 [*]	-0.080 ^{ns}	0.121 ^{ns}
SL	0.310 ^{**}	0.255 [*]	0.417 ^{**}	0.117 ^{ns}		0.235 ^{ns}	0.631 ^{**}	0.305 [*]	0.311 [*]	-0.303 [*]	0.029 ^{ns}
KPS	0.219 [*]	0.048 ^{ns}	0.112 ^{ns}	0.041 ^{ns}	0.208 [*]		0.368 ^{**}	0.299 [*]	0.023 ^{ns}	0.013 ^{ns}	0.303 [*]
SPS	0.396 ^{**}	0.041 ^{ns}	0.305 ^{**}	-0.064 ^{ns}	0.365 ^{**}	0.220 [*]		0.373 ^{**}	-0.063 ^{ns}	-0.316 [*]	0.062 ^{ns}
BY	0.422 ^{**}	0.108 ^{ns}	0.377 ^{**}	0.142 ^{ns}	0.290 ^{**}	0.262 ^{**}	0.228 [*]		0.141 ^{ns}	-0.432 ^{**}	0.561 ^{**}
TSW	-0.051 ^{ns}	0.164 ^{ns}	0.097 ^{ns}	0.277 ^{**}	0.245 [*]	-0.024 ^{ns}	-0.020 ^{ns}	0.135 ^{ns}		0.195 ^{ns}	0.317 [*]
HI	-0.458 ^{**}	-0.021 ^{ns}	-0.332 ^{**}	-0.108 ^{ns}	-0.235 [*]	-0.001 ^{ns}	-0.174 ^{ns}	-0.466 ^{**}	0.133 ^{ns}		0.446 ^{**}
GY	-0.038 ^{ns}	0.011 ^{ns}	-0.017 ^{ns}	0.106 ^{ns}	0.050 ^{ns}	0.261 ^{**}	0.089 ^{ns}	0.531 ^{**}	0.274 ^{**}	0.416 ^{**}	

Note: HD = days to 50% heading, GFP = grain filling period, MD = days to 90% physiological maturity, PH = plant height (cm), SL = spike length (cm), KPS = number of kernels per spike, SPS = number of spikelets per spike, BY= biological yield (kg/plot), GY= grain yield (tone/ha), TSW = thousand seed weight (gm/plot) and HI = harvest index (%).

